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OPR Meta Data Library > Endangered Species Conservation Division (F/PR3... > National ESA Critical Habitat Geodatabase > Acropora retusa >

Coral_AcroporaRetusa_20250715

Entity (ENT) | NMFS Office Of Protected Resources (OPR)

GUID: gov.noaa.nmfs.inport:76807 | Updated: August 1, 2025 |

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Item Identification

Title: Coral_AcroporaRetusa_20250715

Entity Information

Entity Type: Data Table

Active Version?: Yes

Description: A collection of geographic features with the same geometry type.; Source: Esri

Data Attributes

Attribute Summary

		Name	Type	Description
100		OBJECTID	n/a	Internal feature number.; Source: Esri
100		SHAPE	n/a	Feature geometry.; Source: Esri
100		ID	n/a	9 digit unique identifier for each feature in the geodatabase. Used to relate or join supplemental attribute tables.; Source: National Marine Fisheries Service

		Name	Type	Description
	100	SCIENAME	n/a	Binomial or trinomial scientific name. Value formatted as written in the Code of Federal Regulations.; Source: National Marine Fisheries Service
	100	COMNAME	n/a	Legal common name of species. Value formatted as written in the Code of Federal Regulations.; Source: National Marine Fisheries Service
	100	LISTENTITY	n/a	Full text of the ESA listed entity: Species, Subspecies, Distinct Population Segment (DPS), or Evolutionarily Significant Unit (ESU). Value formatted as written in the Code of Federal Regulations. *Note: for entire species listings, this value will be the same as COMNAME value.; Source: National Marine Fisheries Service
	100	LISTSTATUS	n/a	Current Endangered Species Act listing status.; Source: National Marine Fisheries Service
	100	CHSTATUS	n/a	Status of the critical habitat designation.; Source: National Marine Fisheries Service
	100	UNIT	n/a	Critical habitat unit name. Null if designation did not specify units or unit names.; Source: National Marine Fisheries Service
	100	TAXON	n/a	Taxonomic unit.; Source: National Marine Fisheries Service
	100	LEADOFFICE	n/a	Office responsible for the critical habitat Federal Register Notice.; Source: National Marine Fisheries Service
	100	FRN	n/a	Federal Register Notice citation with link to NMFS' webpage for the critical habitat designation (final rule or proposed rule). Volume #, FR, Page Number (Example: 79 FR 39855); Source: National Marine Fisheries Service
	100	PUBDATE	n/a	Federal Register Notice publication date. MM/DD/YYYY format; Source: National Marine Fisheries Service
	100	EFFECTDATE	n/a	Effective date for a final critical habitat designation. Null for proposed critical habitat. MM/DD/YYYY format ; Source: National Marine Fisheries Service

		Name	Type	Description
	100	AREASqKm	n/a	Geodesic area calculated in square kilometers.; Source: National Marine Fisheries Service
	100	CREATEDATE	n/a	Date spatial feature was created or geometry was last edited. MM/DD/YYYY format; Source: National Marine Fisheries Service
	100	NOTES	n/a	Additional information about the feature that is not contained in other fields.; Source: National Marine Fisheries Service
	100	INPORTURL	n/a	Feature class metadata URL. InPort is the National Marine Fisheries Service's official metadata catalog found at: https://inport.nmfs.noaa.gov/inport/ ; Source: National Marine Fisheries Service
	100	SHAPE_Length	n/a	Length of feature in internal units.; Source: Esri
	100	SHAPE_Area	n/a	Area of feature in internal units squared.; Source: Esri
	100	HABTYPE	n/a	Type of habitat; Source: National Marine Fisheries Service
	100	ECFR	n/a	National Marine Fisheries Service; Source: National Marine Fisheries Service

Attribute Details

OBJECTID	CC ID: 1405432
Seq. Order:	1
Data Storage Type:	n/a
Required:	No
Primary Key:	No
Status:	Active
Description:	Internal feature number.; Source: Esri
Allowed Values:	Sequential unique whole numbers that are automatically generated.

SHAPE

CC ID: 1405433

Seq. Order:	2
Data Storage Type:	n/a
Required:	No
Primary Key:	No
Status:	Active
Description:	Feature geometry.; Source: Esri
Allowed Values:	Coordinates defining the features.

ID

CC ID: 1405434

Seq. Order:	3
Data Storage Type:	n/a
Required:	No
Primary Key:	No
Status:	Active
Description:	9 digit unique identifier for each feature in the geodatabase. Used to relate or join supplemental attribute tables.; Source: National Marine Fisheries Service

SCIENAME

CC ID: 1405435

Seq. Order:	4
Data Storage Type:	n/a
Required:	No
Primary Key:	No

Status: Active

Description: Binomial or trinomial scientific name.

Value formatted as written in the Code of Federal Regulations.; Source: National Marine Fisheries Service

COMNAME

CC ID: 1405436

Seq. Order: 5

Data Storage Type: n/a

Required: No

Primary Key: No

Status: Active

Description: Legal common name of species.

Value formatted as written in the Code of Federal Regulations.; Source: National Marine Fisheries Service

LISTENTITY

CC ID: 1405437

Seq. Order: 6

Data Storage Type: n/a

Required: No

Primary Key: No

Status: Active

Description: Full text of the ESA listed entity: Species, Subspecies, Distinct Population Segment (DPS), or Evolutionarily Significant Unit (ESU).

Value formatted as written in the Code of Federal Regulations.

*Note: for entire species listings, this value will be the same as COMNAME value.; Source: National Marine Fisheries Service

LISTSTATUS

CC ID: 1405438

Seq. Order:	7
Data Storage Type:	n/a
Required:	No
Primary Key:	No
Status:	Active
Description:	Current Endangered Species Act listing status.; Source: National Marine Fisheries Service
Allowed Values:	Delisted: Species that were removed from the Endangered Species Act list.; Endangered: Species that are in danger of extinction throughout all or a significant portion of their range.; Threatened: Species that are likely to become endangered in the foreseeable future.;

CHSTATUS

CC ID: 1405439

Seq. Order:	8
Data Storage Type:	n/a
Required:	No
Primary Key:	No
Status:	Active
Description:	Status of the critical habitat designation.; Source: National Marine Fisheries Service
Allowed Values:	Final: A final rule in the Federal Register publishes the regulatory text in full with an effective date. The regulatory text sets out amendments to the Code of Federal Regulations (CFR).; Proposed: A proposed rule in the Federal Register notifies the public of a pending regulation. Any person or organization may comment on it during the comment period.;

UNIT

CC ID: 1405440

Seq. Order:	9
Data Storage Type:	n/a
Required:	No
Primary Key:	No
Status:	Active
Description:	Critical habitat unit name. Null if designation did not specify units or unit names.; Source: National Marine Fisheries Service

TAXON

CC ID: 1405441

Seq. Order:	10
Data Storage Type:	n/a
Required:	No
Primary Key:	No
Status:	Active
Description:	Taxonomic unit.; Source: National Marine Fisheries Service
Allowed Values:	baleen whale: Any of a suborder (Mysticeti) of large whales that have baleen plates in the upper jaw which are used to filter chiefly small crustaceans out of large quantities of seawater.; fish: Any of numerous cold-blooded strictly aquatic craniate vertebrates that include the bony fishes and the cartilaginous and jawless fishes and that have typically an elongated somewhat spindle-shaped body terminating in a broad caudal fin, limbs in the form of fins when present at all, and a 2-chambered heart by which blood is sent through thoracic gills to be oxygenated.; invertebrate: Any animal that lacks a spinal column.; marine reptile: Any of a class (Reptilia) of cold-blooded, air-breathing, usually egg-laying vertebrates that have adapted for an aquatic or semiaquatic life in a marine environment and have a body typically covered with scales or bony plates and a

bony skeleton with a single occipital condyle, a distinct quadrate bone usually immovably articulated with the skull, and ribs attached to the sternum.; pinniped: Any of an order or suborder (Pinnipedia) of aquatic carnivorous mammals with all four limbs modified into flippers.; plant: Any of a kingdom (Plantae) of multicellular eukaryotic mostly photosynthetic organisms typically lacking locomotive movement or obvious nervous or sensory organs and possessing cellulose cell walls.; toothed whale: Any of a suborder (Odontoceti) of cetaceans bearing usually numerous simple conical teeth.;

LEADOFFICE

CC ID: 1405442

Seq. Order: 11

Data Storage Type: n/a

Required: No

Primary Key: No

Status: Active

Description: Office responsible for the critical habitat Federal Register Notice.; Source: National Marine Fisheries Service

Allowed Values: Alaska Region: Includes Alaska and adjacent marine waters extending outwards to the 200 nautical mile boundary of the Exclusive Economic Zone.; Greater Atlantic Region: Includes Minnesota, Wisconsin, Michigan, Illinois, Indiana, Ohio, Kentucky, West Virginia, Pennsylvania, New York, Vermont, New Hampshire, Maine, Massachusetts, Rhode Island, Connecticut, New Jersey, Delaware, Maryland, Virginia, North Carolina (north of Cape Hatteras) and adjacent marine waters extending outwards to the 200 nautical mile boundary of the Exclusive Economic Zone.; Office of Protected Resources: Headquarters office responsible for nationwide conservation, protection, and recovery of endangered and threatened marine species listed under the Endangered Species Act.; Pacific Islands Region: Includes Hawai'i, American Samoa, Guam, the Commonwealth of the Northern Mariana Islands, Kingman Reef, Howland Island, Baker Island, Jarvis Island, Wake Island, Johnston Atoll, Palmyra Atoll and adjacent marine waters extending outwards to the 200 nautical mile boundary of the Exclusive Economic Zone.; Southeast Region: Includes North Carolina (south of Cape Hatteras),

South Carolina, Georgia, Florida, Alabama, Mississippi, Louisiana, Texas, Arkansas, Iowa, Kansas, Kentucky, Missouri, Nebraska, New Mexico, Oklahoma, Tennessee, the Commonwealth of Puerto Rico, the U.S. Virgin Islands and adjacent marine waters extending outwards to the 200 nautical mile boundary of the Exclusive Economic Zone.; West Coast Region: Includes Idaho, Washington, Oregon, California and adjacent marine waters extending outwards to the 200 nautical mile boundary of the Exclusive Economic Zone.;

FRN

CC ID: 1405443

Seq. Order: 12

Data Storage Type: n/a

Required: No

Primary Key: No

Status: Active

Description: Federal Register Notice citation with link to NMFS' webpage for the critical habitat designation (final rule or proposed rule).

Volume #, FR, Page Number (Example: 79 FR 39855); Source: National Marine Fisheries Service

PUBDATE

CC ID: 1405444

Seq. Order: 13

Data Storage Type: n/a

Required: No

Primary Key: No

Status: Active

Description: Federal Register Notice publication date.

MM/DD/YYYY format; Source: National Marine Fisheries Service

EFFECTDATE

CC ID: 1405445

Seq. Order:	14
Data Storage Type:	n/a
Required:	No
Primary Key:	No
Status:	Active
Description:	Effective date for a final critical habitat designation. Null for proposed critical habitat. MM/DD/YYYY format ; Source: National Marine Fisheries Service

AREASqKm

CC ID: 1405446

Seq. Order:	15
Data Storage Type:	n/a
Required:	No
Primary Key:	No
Status:	Active
Description:	Geodesic area calculated in square kilometers.; Source: National Marine Fisheries Service

CREATEDATE

CC ID: 1405447

Seq. Order:	16
Data Storage Type:	n/a
Required:	No
Primary Key:	No

Status: Active

Description: Date spatial feature was created or geometry was last edited.

MM/DD/YYYY format; Source: National Marine Fisheries Service

NOTES

CC ID: 1405448

Seq. Order: 17

Data Storage Type: n/a

Required: No

Primary Key: No

Status: Active

Description: Additional information about the feature that is not contained in other fields.; Source: National Marine Fisheries Service

INPORTURL

CC ID: 1405449

Seq. Order: 18

Data Storage Type: n/a

Required: No

Primary Key: No

Status: Active

Description: Feature class metadata URL.

InPort is the National Marine Fisheries Service's official metadata catalog found at:

<https://inport.nmfs.noaa.gov/inport/>; Source: National Marine Fisheries Service

SHAPE_Length

CC ID: 1405450

Seq. Order: 19

Data Storage	n/a
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Type:	
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Required:	No
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Primary Key:	No
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Status:	Active
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Description:	Length of feature in internal units.; Source: Esri
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Allowed Values:	Positive real numbers that are automatically generated.
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SHAPE_Area

CC ID: 1405451

Seq. Order:	20
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Data Storage Type:	n/a
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Required:	No
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Primary Key:	No
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Status:	Active
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Description:	Area of feature in internal units squared.; Source: Esri
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Allowed Values:	Positive real numbers that are automatically generated.
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HABTYPE

CC ID: 1405452

Seq. Order:	21
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Data Storage Type:	n/a
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Required:	No
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Primary Key:	No
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Status:	Active
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Description:	Type of habitat; Source: National Marine Fisheries Service
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Seq. Order:	22
Data Storage Type:	n/a
Required:	No
Primary Key:	No
Status:	Active
Description:	National Marine Fisheries Service; Source: National Marine Fisheries Service

Catalog Details

Catalog Item ID: 76807

GUID: gov.noaa.nmfs.inport:76807

Metadata Record Created By: Jennifer Schultz

Metadata Record Created: 2025-08-01 20:25+0000

Metadata Record Last Modified By: Jennifer Schultz

Metadata Record Last Modified: 2025-08-01 20:25+0000

Metadata Record Published: 2025-08-01

Owner Org: OPR

Metadata Publication Status: Published Externally

Do Not Publish?:	N
Metadata Review Frequency:	1 Year

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Release 6.0.5

Build FINAL (2025-12-02 18:25 UTC)

